

Substance Use Outcome, Reasons and Preventive Measures: Exploratory Evidence from a Local Government Area in Lagos Nigeria

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Abstract

Recent developments indicate that substance use has noticeably intensified worldwide remarkably in developing nations. The aim of the study was to determine the awareness of people on the potential danger of substance use, reasons why people of dissimilar characteristics get themselves involved in substance use and the various known measures of preventing substance use as utilised by private and public institutions. A structured field survey methodology was used for the study and 243 residents of Yaba Local Government Development Area in Lagos, Nigeria served as participants. The findings of the study revealed that the participants were aware of the potential danger of substance use, the majority of the participants cited the taking of substances to feel high as the foremost reason for engagement in substance use and the participants indicated that all the study preventive measures are known to them with proximity control being the most recognised indicated. The study concludes with the recommendation of broader and longitudinal studies of 'Lagosians' to determine rate of substance use and accompanying risk and protective factors.

Keywords: Substance use, Preventive measures, Proximity control, Reasons for substance abuse, Risk factors, Lagos

Introduction

If there is anything that is profoundly needed in this changing world, it is information affecting personal and social well-being. Such is the information on risk-taking behaviours such as substance use which is one of the difficulties facing Nigeria today irrespective of the user's age (Ojule & Te-Erebe, 2022). Recent developments indicate that substance use has noticeably intensified worldwide remarkably in developing nations (Ajayi & Somefun, 2020; Babalola et al., 2013; Gebreslassie et al., 2013; Srivastava et al. 2021). The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) in 2018 emphatically stated that Nigeria is one of the current topmost consumers of cannabis and amphetamine in Africa. In 2021, the World Health Organisation (2021) reports that the harmful use of alcohol in Africa results in 3.3 million deaths per year. UNODC further stated that in Nigeria, one in seven persons (aged 15–64 years) had used a drug in the past year and 14.4% of Nigerians are presently engaged in drug abuse. Substance use appeals to entities such as government, non-governmental institutions, parents, and teachers (Jatau et al., 2021; Namadi, 2016) and different fields of study such as psychology, sociology, medicine and information science.

Substance use is the detrimental use of psychoactive substances, together with lawful and unlawful drugs, other than which are medically indicated (Srivastava et al., 2021; World Health Organisation, 2021). The National Cancer Institute (n.d.) defines psychoactive substances as drugs or other substances that affect how the brain works and causes changes in mood, awareness, thoughts, feelings, or behaviour. Psychoactive substances include alcohol, cannabis, cocaine, opioids, heroin, hemp, among others. The Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (2022) refers to illicit drug use as the use and misuse of illegal and controlled drugs. WorkplaceTesting (2019)

explains illicit drugs as falling into two groups. The first group is composed of those drugs that are unlawful to process, sell, and consume including cocaine and heroin. The second group comprises those drugs that are lawful to process, sell, and consume when approved by a physician, but are then abused by individuals to whom the drugs have been given, or are used by persons not under a recommending doctor's care, and who perhaps acquired the drugs by unlawful means. The drugs in the second group can consist of prescription pain medication and prescription sedatives.

The health consequences of substance use increase with the frequency and quantity of use and awkward substance use most evidently harms the health of users (Degenhardt, 2012; Osman et al., 2016). Substance abuse not only affects health, education and occupational career (McLellan, 2017; Qureshi et al., 2014), but it also incurs a huge financial and social burden on the society (Ningombam et al., 2011; Musa et al., 2022). Alcohol and drug abuse obstructs cognitive and emotional development, increases the chance of accidental injury and death, leads to sexual assaults and unsafe sex, lowers grade, and increases the possibility of drug dependency (Bajwa et al., 2013; Blanco et al., 2016; Mohammadpoorasl et al., 2014; White & Hingson, 2014). People with substance use disorder are more likely to die younger and are more likely to have a psychiatric disorder than people without substance use disorder (Di Forti et al., 2013; Makanjuola et al., 2014; Volkow et al., 2014). Substance use increases the chances of sexually transmitted infections (Amoo et al., 2020), polydrug use (Musa et al., 2022) and depression and threat of unemployment after college (Arria et al., 2013a). It is also connected with a number of adverse consequences in young adulthood, including undesirable sexual encounters, legal consequences and suicide (Arria et al., 2013b; Ritchwood et al., 2015) and criminal activity (Osman et al., 2016; Pierce et al. 2017)

Although substance use is believed to be a growing problem in Nigeria, there is no published data on the awareness of people of the potential danger of substance abuse, reasons why people of dissimilar age groups get themselves involved in excessive substance abuse and the various known methods of preventing substance use as utilised by private and public institutions. This is particularly important among different people that are not necessarily university students but educated as to be aware of the potential dangers of substance abuse. Among the gap from the literature as identified by Jatau et al. (2021) is that most of the epidemiological studies were carried out among secondary school students. Very few studies were performed among the overall population to isolate other predisposed categories of people involved in substance use. This study, therefore, in understanding this knowledge gap explored a local government in South-West Nigeria as a point of reference.

Objectives of the study

The overall objective of the study was to investigate substance use among diverse groups of people having varying socio-demographic features and known preventive measures in a local government development area in Lagos, Nigeria, at an exploratory level, in order to provoke further research and inform policy formulation and action. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. find out the awareness of participants on the potential danger of substance use.
2. identify the reasons why people get themselves involved in substance abuse.
3. determine the various methods known to the participants that they have seen or observed as used by private and public institutions for the prevention of substance use.

Review of related literature

Majority of substance use studies have been on university students (Ajayi & Somefun, 2020; Amoo et al., 2020; Bajwa et al., 2013; Cho et al., 2015; Gomel et al., 2013; Gupta et al. 2013; Idris et al., 2018; Locke et al., 2015; Mohammadpoorasl et al. 2014; Osman et al., 2016; White & Hingson, 2014; Yi et al., 2017). This is not unconnected to the danger of substance use being prevalent among the adolescents (Babalola et al., 2013; Makanjuola et al., 2014). Males have also been found to be involved in substance use than females (Adamson et al., 2015; Aguocho et al., 2020; Ajayi &

Somefun, 2020; Ansari et al., 2015; Anyanwu et al., 2016; Babalola et al., 2013; Bajwa et al., 2013; Gomes et al., 2013; Idris et al., 2018; Jaisooriya et al., 2016; Mahanta et al., 2016; Mohammadpoorasl et al., 2013; Mohammadpoorasl et al., 2014; Yi et al., 2017).

Gupta et al. (2013) carried out a study among male university students and substance use prevalence was seen in more than half of the students who were in the age group 19-21 years. Among the users, alcohol users were most common, followed by smokers, tobacco chewers and cannabis users. None of the students reported use of cocaine, amphetamine, sedatives or heroin. More than two thirds of the users cited that they shared substances with their friends. In a recent study, in support of the preceding study, Offie et al. (2022) in a cross-sectional descriptive study carried out among young people aged 10-24 years in South-West, Nigeria showed that the most commonly used substance by the respondents was alcoholic beverages followed by cigarettes, cannabis, and tramadol. Adamson et al. (2015) in their cross-sectional survey of drug use among Nigeria population aged 15-64 years focusing on the six geopolitical zones also demonstrated that alcohol had the highest prevalence rate of use and cannabis was the most frequently used illicit drug. However, in an Iranian study, Mohammadpoorasl et al. (2013) indicated that smoking was the familiar substance use behaviour with a prevalence rate of 15.8% while Mohammadpoorasl et al. (2014) showed for the measurement done in past 30 days that cannabis is the most used substance.

In an Indian study, Mahanta et al. (2016) aimed at estimating the pervasiveness of alcohol takers among school-going youthful students in an industrial town. Significantly higher number of youthful students (≥ 15 years) took alcohol in comparison to children (< 15 years). Anyanwu et al. (2016) determined the prevalence and pattern of substance abuse among secondary school students in South-East, Nigeria and they identified that alcohol was the most commonly abused substance. Abuse of alcohol, cigarette and kolanut were significantly more in 15–19 years old. Nahvisadeh et al. (2014) considered seven articles about high school students within 14-19 years from Iranian databases. From these articles, the highest drug use was cigarette followed by alcohol and heroin. Ojule (2022) in his study of substance use by secondary school students in urban and rural settings of a local government area in South-South, Nigeria uncovered that alcohol was the most frequently abused in both settings. Largely, in a scoping review focusing on Nigeria, Jatau et al. (2021) indicated that the most recurrently incriminated drugs, constantly reported by the majority of the studies were cannabis (it should be noted that *hemp is a specific type of cannabis*), codeine, amphetamine, heroin, cocaine, and tramadol. The observed substance use variation in different persons and groups in the aforementioned studies is due to some risk and protective factors.

McLellan (2017) argues that an individual's susceptibility to substance use can be predicted by assessing the nature and number of personal and environmental risk and protective factors. Gupta et al. (2013) identifies substance use risk factors as social demographic factors such as age, parental education, occupation and socio-economic status. Degenhardt (2012) mentions that substance use risk factors can be split into social and contextual factors, family factors, individual factors, and peer affiliations during adolescence. Several risk factors linked with illicit drug use among university students have been identified in different countries. These factors also include socio-demographic characteristics such as male gender (El Ansari et al., 2015; Mohammadpoorasl et al., 2014; Osman et al., 2016), high family income (Bajwa et al., 2013), living on or off campus, living in an upper-middle- or high-income country (Peltzer & Pengpid, 2016) and financial burden (El Ansari et al., 2015). Among the protective factors, living away from campus and/or living with their parents, and having better health and health awareness seem connected with lower illicit drug use (Babalola et al., 2013; Gomes et al., 2013; Mohammadpoorasl et al., 2014; Suerken et al., 2014). More identified protective factors include older age (Bajwa et al., 2013; Peltzer & Pengpid, 2016), higher level of religiosity (Gomes et al., 2013; Peltzer & Pengpid, 2016) and living with parents (Mohammadpoorasl et al., 2014).

Degenhardt (2012) highlights that the indicators of substance use entails: strong desire to take the substance; compromised control over use; withdrawal syndrome on cessation or reduction

of use; forbearance to the effects of the drug; the need for larger doses to reach the desired psychological effect; uneven amount of time spent by the user in getting, using, and recovering from drug use; and persistent drug taking despite the problems that occur. As regards the reasons for substance use, Osman et al. (2016) stated that curiosity was the main reason for initiation of substance use and peers were the prime source among university students. Gupta et al. (2013) cited reasons such as relief from psychological stress, followed by an easy availability as most common reasons for substance use. Gupta et al. added that affordability, peer influence and decrease in tiredness were also among the common reasons. Kvillemo et al. (2021), in their study of high school students from wealthy cities discovered that the most prominent motive for substance use turned up to be a desire to feel a part of the social setting and to have high social status within the peer group. Ojule and Te-Erebe (2022) in their study of secondary school students in urban and rural settings of a local government area in South-South, Nigeria cited the reasons for substance use as being awake, curiosity and peer pressure.

As stated earlier, most studies on substance use have covered respondents in universities and recommended preventive measures without looking at existing preventive measures – how familiar they are to the respondents with the way private and public institutions have employed them in addressing the neglect of this menace in the society. These suggested preventive strategies are not directly itemised by the study respondents or at the least confirmed to be known by the respondents as possible proactive way out. For instance, among the conclusions of various studies, applying and revisiting preventive measures have been prioritised. Bajwa et al. (2013) mentioned that their study is expected to guide the design and implementation of preventive measures. Shepardson and Hustad (2015) concluded that the risk factors uncovered in their study may be effective targets for preventing increases in substance use. Further, Srivastava et al. (2021) also suggested the need for community- and household-level programmatic mediations to lessen the danger of substance use among youngsters.

To consider some of the preventive strategies that extant studies have mentioned, Osman et al. (2016) emphasised that the responsibility of the university and parents in observing and providing education to enhance awareness of substances and their consequences is key. Jiloha et al. (2017), in a methodical review on the effectiveness of prevention of substance use identified taxation, minimum legal age, public consumption bans and restriction on advertisements. Tools such as school-based prevention and skill-training mediations are also effectual in reducing substance use among adolescents. However, Jiloha et al. underlined that social norms and intervention do not have strong indication of efficacy in substance use diminution among adolescents. Kvillemo et al. (2021) stressed that students reported universal information-based prevention to be irrelevant and vacillated on the use of selective prevention mediations due to panic of being reported to authorities. The study suggested that universal prevention should point toward reliable information from credible sources, firmer substance control measures, parental involvement, and social leisure activities without substance use. In addition, suggested selective prevention includes guaranteed confidentiality and non-judging encounters when seeking help. Nath et al. (2022) advocated for severe policy and programme guidelines to curb substance use societal menace. Offie et al. (2022) added that intervention strategies aimed at reducing the rate of substance use among the younger population should be utmost, especially in the field of health education.

The Department of Health of the State of Hawaii (n.d.) recognises several effective strategies for preventing substance use, particularly when combined. They include: (1) information dissemination – the provision of awareness and knowledge of the nature and extent of substance use; (2) preventive education – intends to affect critical life, decision making, refusal skills and social skills; (3) alternatives – involves the participation of targeted populations in activities that exclude any substance that is misused; (4) problem identification and referral – entails identification, education, and counselling for those who have indulged in substance use or first timers; (5) community-based process – targeted at improving the ability of the community to

provide prevention and treatment services to substance use disorders more effectively using helping activities; and (6) environmental approach – method setting up or changing written and unwritten community standards, codes and attitudes, eventually affecting incidence and prevalence of substance use challenges in the general population. Lopez et al. (2021) enunciated group methods of substance use control such as contingency management, cognitive therapy, drug counselling, family therapy, motivational interviewing, recovery training, and social support, among others. Other substance abuse preventive measures are: proximity control – involves reducing disengaged or disruptive behaviour with the assistance of an instructor and positive inducement/reinforcement – encompasses tackling reinforcing behaviour as substance use with healthier incentives such as reward for substance use self-restraint.

Theoretical standpoint

This study is patterned based on two relevant theories – the ecological systems theory and the problem behaviour theory. The ecological systems theory was developed by the psychologist Urie Bronfenbrenner in the late 1970s determinedly recognising that individuals affect and are affected by a multifaceted range of social influences and encapsulated environmental interactions. According to Bronfenbrenner (1979) and *Bronfenbrenner & Morris (2007)*, the theory pinpoints five environmental systems with which an individual interacts. They are: (1) microsystem: this concerns the institutions and groups that most immediately and directly impact the individual's development including: family, school, religious institutions, neighbourhood, and peers; (2) mesosystem: this comprises relationships between the microsystems, for instance between the individual's peers and the family; (3) exosystem: this entails connections between social settings that do not involve the individual; (4) macrosystem: this depicts the all-embracing culture that influences the developing individual, as well as the microsystems and mesosystems tacit in those cultures. Cultural contexts can differ based on geographic location, socioeconomic status, poverty, and ethnicity. It is important to state that macrosystems change across time (Kail & Cavanaugh, 2010); and (5) chronosystem: this incorporates the pattern of environmental events and transitions over the life course, as well as changing socio-historical circumstances.

Problem behaviour theory (PBT) is a systematic, multivariate, social-psychological conceptual framework derived initially from the fundamental concepts of value and expectation in social learning theory by Rotter and the concept of anomie by Merton. The underlying presumption of the theory is that all behaviour is the result of person-environment interaction. It is the revised framework in the late 1960s involving a longitudinal study of the socialisation of problem behaviour among secondary school students and college students (Jessor & Jessor, 1977) that is most widely recognised and mentioned in academics. PBT assists to explain the development and nature of problem behaviours, for instance, alcohol use (Jessor & Jessor, 1977; Jessor, 2001). This kind of behaviour digresses from both social and legal customs. The model comprises three systems of psychosocial influences: personality system (all social cognitions, personal values, expectations, beliefs, and values), perceived environmental system (family and peer expectations), and the behaviour system (problem and conventional behavioural structures that work in opposition to each other). Demographic and socialisation variables affect the personality and perceived environmental systems and have an indirect impact on behaviour. The personality and perceived environment systems are viewed as proximal or more direct determinants of behaviour than are demographic and socialisation variables.

This study absorbs elements of these environmental systems into its socio-demographic variables, reasons why individuals get themselves involved in substance abuse and the diverse preventive measures. Problem behaviours are also seen in the substance use of alcohol, cigarette, hemp, heroin and depressants.

Materials and methods

A survey research design aimed at obtaining primary data was used for this study. Primary data were collected from participants through the use of a structured questionnaire. The study was also exploratory in nature simply because it was set out to get preliminary information and attain a better understanding on the subject and identify potential areas of future research. The study was designed to target participants that had moderate level of education (at least Secondary School Leaving Certificate) up to the possible highest level of education (doctorate degree). This was because the instrument was written in English language (the common language of communication among the educated in Nigeria) and to determine possible variations along socio-demographic variables particularly academic qualification. The education factor also informed the choice of area for the study - the Yaba Local Council Development Area where the University of Lagos is. According to the Lagos State Government (2020), based on the last population census in 2006, the population of Lagos Mainland Local Government under which Yaba Local Government Development Area is categorised, is 629,469 (comprising 326,433 males and 303,036 females).

The study was conducted during the months of November 2020 and March of 2021. A two-stage sampling method was engaged to draw a manageable sample size. Firstly, using systematic sampling technique, 545 participants were approached from 20 streets around the University of Lagos for participation in the study, out of which 146 did not consent for inclusion citing reasons such as lack of interest in the subject and time constraint. In choosing the streets, it was ensured that the selected streets had nothing less than 20 dwellings where people lived. Systematic sampling allowed participants to be analytically chosen from different houses in different streets to ensure a fairly representative sample of the population. The participants were approached and selected on the basis of certain sorting criteria. The criteria for participant inclusion were: (1) he/she must have abused or closely known someone who has abused at least one of the substances (alcohol, cigarette, hemp, heroin and depressants) listed for the study at a point in time (2) must not be less than 18 years; and (3) must possess at least Secondary School Leaving Certificate. This condition was relevant because participants were educated on the potential danger and possible preventive measures of substance use by way of discussion and pictorial representation. Out of the 399 consenting participants, 280 were finally included for participation in the study due to the lack of funds. The next stage involved a purposive sampling strategy (second sampling method) to ensure that the desired 280 study participants were obtained from the purposely chosen local government development area. This involved seven streets around the University of Lagos from which 40 participants already consented per street in taking part in the study - making 280 participants in all. The structured questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A determined the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants. These included data on age, marital status, educational attainment, religious affiliation, ethnic background and occupation. Section B determined the level of agreement of the participants with: (1) how aware the participants are of the potential danger of substance abuse (that is, alcohol, cigarette, hemp, heroin and depressants); (2) the reason(s) why people get themselves involved in substance use; and (3) the various methods known to the participants that they have seen or observed that private and public institutions use for the prevention of substance use.

The authors ensured that all procedures contributing to this work complied with the ethical standards of the relevant national committees on human experimentation. Before distributing the questionnaire, the objectives of the study were explained to the participants. Confidentiality of the responses was ensured. This was achieved by using anonymous copies of the questionnaire. Participation in the study was voluntary and written informed consents were obtained from all the participants before the administration of the instrument.

A pilot study was carried out at Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos State employing 40 participants having similar characteristics to the main participants using residents of two streets

close to Lagos State University, Ojo. The purpose of the pilot test was to (1) examine the feasibility of the questionnaire and (2) collect data to examine its reliability. Ultimately, the pilot test feedback was used to rework the instrument. A four-point Likert-type scale of two types was used: 1 = strongly unaware, 2 = unaware, 3 = aware and 4 = strongly aware; and 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = agree, and 4 = strongly agree. An estimated reliability coefficient of .89, as computed by Cronbach’s alpha coefficient, attested to the internal consistency of the items measured.

Table 1: Sample size

Street	Study Population	Sample (Final figure used for the study)
Street A	40	37
Street B	40	40
Street C	40	34
Street D	40	32
Street E	40	40
Street F	40	31
Street G	40	39
	270	243

*Street name not included for the purpose of anonymity

The desired 280 copies of the questionnaire were distributed by the researchers with the assistance of three well trained research assistants who helped in the administration and collection of the copies of the questionnaire. From the 280 copies, 13 were not returned and 14 were invalid because they were not appropriately filled. Hence, 243 copies were finally analysed representing a response rate of 86.8%. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 15 was used for each questionnaire and responses entered. Participants’ socio-demographic characteristics and other study constructs were reported as frequencies and percentages. For the purpose of believability, Makinde and Makinde (2020) and Sullivan (2013) underlined that descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, have unclear meanings when applied to Likert scale responses. Hence, the suitability of the addition of frequencies (percentages of responses) for analysis of ordinal data as used in the study.

Findings of the study

The socio-demographic characteristics of the participants were identified in terms of age range, marital status, education, religion, ethnicity and occupation. Table 2 presents the age range, marital status, education, religion, ethnicity and occupation of the participants. The majority (125: 51.4%) of the participants were within the age range of 18-27 years (the highest) and 28 (11.5%) were in the age range >48 years. More than one third of the participants (114: 46.9%) were single, with less than a tenth of the participants (22: 9.1%) being widow. Over one third (113: 46.5%) of the participants were holders first degree/Higher National Diploma (HND) while 8.6% of the participants had GCE/WAEC/Equivalent qualification. Participants were asked to indicate their religion. More than half of the participants (130: 53.5%) were Christians whereas just 1.6% of the participants (the lowest) belonged to other religions apart from Islam and Traditional Religion. The majority of the participants (110: 45.3%) were of the Yoruba race. This is definitely connected to the study being carried out in South-West Nigeria where the Yoruba people are predominant. In terms of occupation, there was a tie between two occupations, participants who were civil servants and those having other jobs [apart from working in private firm and self employed] constituted the majority (76: 31.3%).

Table 2: Socio-demographic background of participants (N=243)

Variable	Classification	Frequency	Percentage
Age range	18-27 years	125	51.4
	28-37 years	56	23.0
	38-47 years	34	14.1
	>48 years	28	11.5
Marital status	Single	114	46.9
	Married	80	32.9
	Divorced/Separated	27	11.1

Education	Widow	22	9.1
	Postgraduate (PGD/Master/PhD)	75	30.9
	Bachelor/HND	113	46.5
	Diploma/OND/Equivalent	34	14.0
Religion	WAEC/GCE/Equivalent	21	8.6
	Christianity	130	53.5
	Islam	67	27.6
	Traditional Worshipper	42	17.3
Ethnicity	Others	4	1.6
	Yoruba	110	45.3
	Igbo	69	28.4
	Hausa	45	18.5
Occupation	Others	19	7.8
	Civil Servant	31	12.7
	Self Employed	76	31.3
	Private Firm	60	24.7
	Others	76	31.3

Source: Field Data, 2020

Participants were asked about their awareness of the potential danger of substance use. After adding up the two levels that showed that the participants were aware of the potential danger of substance use, that is, aware and strongly aware, high percentages of awareness were indicated by the respondents for all substances (alcohol, cigarette, hemp, heroin and depressants). The participants were mostly aware of the potential danger of cigarette (93.9%). The substance that the participants were least aware of its potential danger was heroin (65%). Table 3 illustrates the responses on the participants' awareness of the potential danger of substance use.

Table 3: Participants awareness of the potential danger of substance use (N=243)

Substance	Level	Frequency	%	Σ%
Alcohol	Strongly Aware	70	28.8	92.6
	Aware	155	63.8	
	Unaware	11	4.5	
	Strongly Unaware	7	2.9	
Cigarette	Strongly Aware	118	48.6	93.9
	Aware	110	45.3	
	Unaware	7	2.8	
	Strongly Unaware	8	3.3	
Hemp	Strongly Aware	111	45.8	83.2
	Aware	91	37.4	
	Unaware	28	11.5	
	Strongly Unaware	13	5.3	
Heroin	Strongly Aware	77	31.7	65.0
	Aware	81	33.3	
	Unaware	62	25.5	
	Strongly Unaware	23	9.5	
Depressants	Strongly Aware	94	38.7	75.3
	Aware	89	36.6	
	Unaware	38	15.6	
	Strongly Unaware	22	9.1	

Source: Field Data, 2020

*Σ% means summation of the first two levels of awareness

The study further sought to find out the reasons why participants get themselves involved in substance use. With the benchmark of using the summation of the first two levels of agreement, the majority of the participants (83.2%) cited the taking of substances to feel high as the foremost reason for engagement in substance use. This was closely followed by the reason of pleasing friends taking the same substance (81.9%). The least reason why participants get involved in substance use

was seeing people using them on television (57.2%). The breakdown of other responses on reasons for involvement in substance use is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Reasons why participants get themselves involved in substance use (N=243)

Substance	Level	Frequency	%	Σ%
Pleasing Friends taking Same Substance	Strongly Agree	57	23.5	81.9
	Agree	142	58.4	
	Disagree	23	9.5	
	Strongly Disagree	21	8.6	
Taking Substance to Feel High	Strongly Agree	132	54.4	83.2
	Agree	70	28.8	
	Disagree	29	11.9	
	Strongly Disagree	12	4.9	
Using Substance as Medicine	Strongly Agree	82	33.7	65.4
	Agree	77	31.7	
	Disagree	66	27.2	
	Strongly Disagree	18	7.4	
Overcome Shyness when Talking to Opposite Sex	Strongly Agree	75	30.8	65.8
	Agree	85	35.0	
	Disagree	52	21.4	
	Strongly Disagree	31	12.8	
Saw People Using them on Television	Strongly Agree	76	31.3	57.2
	Agree	63	25.9	
	Disagree	43	17.7	
	Strongly Disagree	61	25.1	

Source: Field Data, 2020

The study also identified the various measures known to the participants that have been employed by private and public institutions for the prevention of substance use. All the preventive measures that were put before the participants for confirmation based on the summation of the first two levels of agreement had high percentages. Well above two third of the participants indicated that all the preventive measures are known to them. A total of 208 (85.5%) of the participants indicated proximity control as the most recognised. This was followed by systematic dissemination on the addicts (81.9%). The least used control measure for the prevention of substance use as judged by the participants was group counselling procedures and modelling. Both preventive measures tied as indicated by 172 participants (70.8%). Table 5 presents the detailed information on preventive measures employed by private and public institutions as indicated by the participants.

Table 5: Employment of various measures by private and public institutions for prevention of substance use (N=243)

Substance	Level	Frequency	%	Σ%
Systematic Dissemination on the Addicts	Strongly Agree	89	36.6	81.9
	Agree	110	45.3	
	Disagree	24	9.9	
	Strongly Disagree	20	8.2	
Group Counselling Procedures	Strongly Agree	69	28.4	70.8
	Agree	103	42.4	
	Disagree	39	16.0	
	Strongly Disagree	32	13.2	
Inducement/Reinforcement	Strongly Agree	82	33.8	76.2
	Agree	103	42.4	
	Disagree	37	15.2	
	Strongly Disagree	21	8.6	
Proximity Control	Strongly Agree	117	48.1	85.5
	Agree	91	37.4	
	Disagree	20	8.3	
	Strongly Disagree	15	6.2	
Modelling	Strongly Agree	84	34.6	70.8
	Agree	88	36.2	
	Disagree	40	16.5	
	Strongly Disagree	31	12.7	

Source: Field Data, 2020

Discussion

It was realised from the study that the study participants were predominantly (51.4%) between the age range of 18-27 years. Gupta et al. (2013) confirmed this by indicating that more than half of the respondents who abused substances were in the age group of 19-21 years. A similar study in South-West Nigeria by Offie et al. (2022) revealed that young people aged 10-24 years abused substance like alcohol, cigarettes and cannabis. These results show the applicability of the current study indicating that the results are relevant to contemporary substance use.

Regarding the awareness of participants on the potential danger of substance use, previous studies have shown a visible trend of substance use among young people who are predominant in the present study. Adamson et al. (2015), Anyanwu et al. (2016), Gupta et al. (2013), Jatau et al. (2021), Mohammadpoorasl et al. (2013), Mohammadpoorasl et al. (2014), Nahvisadeh et al. (2014), Offie et al. (2022) and Ojule (2022) in their various studies have pointed to alcohol, cigarette and cannabis [*hemp is a specific type of cannabis*] as the most abused substances. The awareness on the potential danger of these frequent substances must have been as a result of participants consciously seeking for information on them with users also suffering from some health issues attached to usage in the past.

The study also found that taking substance to feel high and please friends who take same substance are the commonest reasons for engagement in substance use. Studies such as Gupta et al. (2013), Kvillemo et al. (2021), Ojule and Te-Erebe (2022) and Osman et al. (2016) lend credence to the current study by variously mentioning peer pressure/influence and desire to be a part of a social setting/social status and curiosity that are attached to young people trying to measure up with their friends.

The most common preventive measures known to the participants are proximity control and systematic dissemination on the addict. As much as group counselling procedures is also recognised by the participants as supported by Srivastava et al. (2021) who clamoured for community- and household-level programmatic mediations to ease substance use, the participants in the current study show preference for personal-directed prevention measures. This is in agreement with Bajwa et al. (2013) pointing to the use of prevention measures that must be study directed for better results and Kvillemo et al. (2021) who recommended the employment of selective prevention mediations due to panic of being reported to authorities.

Conclusions

Our results show fairly well informed participants on substance use in this local government area. Though it could be as a result of our educating the participants before the study, however, this is a pointer to the fact that health education should be periodically organised by private and public institutions to enhance the possibility of health-conscious populace. Considering that the participants' responses to the study questions and substance use education are on the high side, this could be a sign of indulgence in some substances, consequently, broader and longitudinal studies of 'Lagosians' are suggested to determine rate of substance use and accompanying risk and protective factors. The results of this study can be used for planning of further study in this shifting field of study associated with societal influences.

Limitations to the study

Our research has limitations, but the results are encouraging. Since participants were a non-random sample of people, results cannot be generalised to the people of Lagos State and Nigeria. Many factors which are recognised to influence substance use of people of diverse ages were not assessed. Finally, these data are subject to the limitations of self-report. Participants may have had concerns about answering questions on sensitive topics and potentially illicit behaviour, which could have led to underreporting of certain behaviours.

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